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Investigating the Challenges of Digitalization in the Construction Industry Using Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM)

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ABSTRACT

Digitalization in the construction industry has lagged behind many other sectors. Given the significant contribution of this sector to national economies, its slow progress in digital transformation negatively affects not only the construction industry itself but also the overall economic performance of countries. In developing countries in particular, it is essential for construction companies to identify the barriers to digitalization and take necessary measures in order to remain competitive in an increasingly challenging market environment. In this context, the present study addresses five key challenges to digitalization in the construction industry. These challenges were identified through an extensive literature review and evaluated using the Interpretive Structural Modelling (ISM) method based on expert opinions. Based on the hierarchical challenge structure derived from the ISM analysis, the foundational challenges in the digitalization of the construction industry were identified as Applications and Company Management.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Industrial Revolution, which began with the use of steam-powered machines, has reached its fourth phase—referred to as Industry 4.0—characterized by the integration of digitalization. As industrial production has advanced and competition has intensified, enterprises within the manufacturing sector have increasingly focused on establishing efficient production processes and reducing operational costs. In businesses aiming to enhance efficiency in engineering and operations while minimizing costs, digitalization is identified as a strategic priority. The completion of digital transformation encompasses a wide range of disciplines, including lifecycle management, engineering services and design, information technologies (IT), and automation. Taking full advantage of this competitive environment requires the adoption of automation and digitalization solutions, which have become essential components of modern industrial strategies. The successful adoption of digitalization depends on the integration of specialized knowledge from professionals across various fields, working collaboratively to develop optimal solutions [1].

Similar to transformations observed in other production sectors, the integration of technological tools and new fabrication methods—core components of Industry 4.0—into construction projects and their life cycle stages, resulting in increased autonomy and digitalization, is referred to as Construction 4.0. These transformations have contributed to enhanced efficiency in the construction

industry, reduced delays, and improved access to financial resources. Furthermore, they have facilitated improvements in safety, resource efficiency, and overall quality [2,3].

Construction 4.0 facilitates information exchange among project stakeholders, reduces complexities, and enables more effective communication. For these reasons, it contributes to improved quality and increased productivity. However, research and development (R&D) investments in the construction industry remain insufficient today, and technological advancements continue to progress at a slow pace. This slow progress can largely be attributed to the simultaneous execution of numerous processes within construction projects and the involvement of diverse stakeholders (such as engineers, architects, contractors, subcontractors, etc.) at different stages of the process, which introduces significant complexity. Moreover, the temporary and time-limited nature of construction projects, combined with a prevailing short-term mindset in the industry, presents a series of obstacles to innovation [4,5].

In this study, a literature review was conducted to identify the challenges that hinder digitalization in the construction industry. Searches were carried out in the Web of Science (WoS) and Google Scholar databases using relevant keywords such as “digital,” “BIM,” “monitoring,” “technology,” “construction sector,” and “construction industry.” The search results were critically analyzed, and a number of studies considered relevant and aligned with the research objectives were selected. Brief descriptions of the selected studies are presented below.

According to Özmen et al. [5], the construction industry, unlike other manufacturing sectors, operates independently of standardization, which results in a slower integration of autonomous systems. Musarat et al. [6] have identified a lack of awareness and understanding among industry stakeholders regarding the benefits and potential of digitalization in the construction sector. In addition, the shortage of skilled personnel and inadequate training have been found to be other major barriers to the adoption of digital technologies. According to Zhong et al. [7], “top management willingness to transform” is the most critical success factors for digital transformation in the construction industry.

Technologies such as Building Information Modeling (BIM), Digital Twin and Blockchain systems play a pivotal role in advancing the digitalization of the construction sector. Building Information Modeling (BIM) represents the integration of digital technologies in the digitalization of the construction industry [8]. BIM is a digital approach used throughout all stages of construction projects that supports architects, engineers, and designers in generating and sharing information [6,9]. According to Zheng et al. [8], the use of BIM-centered digital technologies in Engineering, Procurement, and Construction (EPC) projects enhances both cost and time performance. BIM offers significant potential for the construction industry by enabling digitalization throughout the entire lifecycle of buildings [6]. Furthermore, the effective implementation of BIM technology in operational processes necessitates hiring new qualified personnel or providing targeted training for the existing workforce [10].

While the literature includes numerous studies supporting this potential and its benefits [11-15], there are also studies that argue otherwise [16-19]. According to Arshad et al. [14], although BIM has achieved progress in certain technical aspects, standardization in contractual and legal matters has yet to be established. Moreover, there is a need for standards and protocols to ensure a common language across BIM software platforms [13].

Sun et al. [20], who conducted research on the application of blockchain technology in the construction industry—one of the other key digitalization systems—found that countries such as the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, and China have made the most significant contributions in this area. The Digital Twin is another key system that offers integrated information by connecting the physical building to its digital counterpart, thereby supporting the full lifecycle of construction projects [21]. It facilitates comprehensive analysis, performance evaluation, and collaborative decision-making among civil engineers, architects, operations managers, and other stakeholders [22]. According to Yang et al., Digital Twins also bring a range of challenges and

requirements, including data management and integration difficulties, ensuring privacy, maintaining security, and the need for upskilling and transforming the technical workforce [23].

The objective of this study is to systematically identify the key challenges to digitalization in the construction sector and organize them in a hierarchical structure based on their relative importance. This study consists of four sections: the literature review in Section 1 examines digitalization and system frameworks in the construction industry; the methodology of the study is presented in Section 2; analyses and their results are provided in Section 3. The final section presents the conclusions.

2 METHODOLOGY

In the first phase of the study, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify the main challenges hindering digitalization in the construction industry. Based on the challenges identified through this review, an online questionnaire was designed and administered to construction professionals. The survey specifically targeted expert civil engineers working in the construction sector. Five selected experts were asked to evaluate the interrelationships among the identified key challenges. The questionnaire consisted of two main sections: the first section collected general background information about the respondents, while the second focused on the key challenges related to the construction sector. The experts were asked to assess the relationships between the listed challenges using a binary approach (i.e., existence or absence of a relationship). Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) was employed to identify the interrelationships and influences among the challenges. In this method, factors are first categorized, and a layered hierarchical model is developed. This model helps in structuring and solving complex problems [24, 25]. One of the key strengths of the ISM method is its ability to include indirect relationships in the analysis [26].

3 ANALYSIS

This section is structured into three main phases: (1) identification of key challenges through a comprehensive literature review, (2) preparation and administration of a structured questionnaire, and (3) development of an interpretive model based on the identified challenges.

3.1 Identification of Key Challenges

In the first phase, a literature review was conducted to compile a comprehensive list of key challenges. Through this review, six key challenges were identified. However, the challenges related to cost management were excluded from the list based on expert opinions, as it was considered a general challenge inherent to most construction projects. The literature-based information on the remaining challenges is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Key Challenges

ID	Indicator	Source
C1	Professionals (Users)	6, 20
C2	Workers	6, 29
C3	Applications	6, 7, 20
C4	Company Management	6, 7, 30
C5	Construction Site Management	6, 20

3.2 Preparation and Administration of a Questionnaire

In the second phase, a questionnaire was developed based on the list of challenges. The key challenges were structured according to the Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) approach, and the relationships among the five challenges were assessed in terms of whether a relationship exists or not. This questionnaire was administered to five experts. All participants in this study hold the professional title of civil engineer. In terms of professional experience within the construction sector, one expert has 0–5 years of experience, two have between 5 and 10 years, and the remaining two have been active for 10 to 15 years. Regarding academic qualifications, two experts hold doctoral degrees, two hold master's degrees, and one holds a bachelor's degree in civil engineering. Furthermore, three of the experts are currently employed in the public sector, while the remaining two are working in the private sector. This diverse distribution in both academic background and professional experience contributes to the comprehensiveness and reliability of the findings derived from their insights.

Expert opinions were obtained individually via an online expert survey. In this process, the experts were asked to assess the interrelationships among the variables, specifically evaluating how each variable is associated with the others. The relationships among the challenges were identified by experts based on a binary assessment of the existence or absence of a connection. In instances where expert opinions diverged, the relationship of difficulty between variables was determined according to the majority consensus.

3.3 Interpretive Model

Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) enables the problem to be clearly defined, simplified, and systematically categorized [25, 27]. ISM analysis generally follows the steps below [28]:

1. Identification of contextual relationships:

Y indicates that variable i has a one-way effect on variable j ; V indicates that variable j affects variable i ; X indicates a mutual relationship between variables i and j ; Z indicates no relationship between i and j .

2. Determination of indirect relationships and formation of the Reachability Matrix:

In the matrix, a value of 0 is assigned for Z, a value of 1 for X, and either 1 or 0 for Y and V, depending on the presence or absence of a relationship.

3. Level partitioning:

The Reachability Set (i), the Antecedent Set (j), and their Intersection are determined to assign levels.

4. Identification of interrelationships:

Based on the matrix and sets, hierarchical relationships among the variables are finalized.

Tables 2, 3 and 4 present the results of the ISM analyses conducted to identify and structure the key challenges associated with digitalization in the construction industry.

Table 2 shows the Contextual Relationships. Table 3 presents the reachability matrix among the identified challenges, with the transitivity assumption examined and the relevant values highlighted in bold. In this table, a value of 1 indicates the presence of a bidirectional relationship between two variables, while a value of 0 denotes no relationship. In the case of unidirectional relationships, a value of 1 is assigned in the direction of influence, and 0 in the opposite direction.

Table 2. Contextual Relationships

	C5	C4	C3	C2
C1	Y	V	V	Z
C2	X	Z	Z	
C3	Y	X		
C4	Y			

Table 3. Reachability Matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	1	0	0	1
C2	0	1	0	0	1
C3	1	1	1	1	1
C4	1	1	1	1	1
C5	0	1	0	0	1

Table 4. Results of Level Partitions

ID	Reachability Set	Antecedent Set	Intersection	Level
C1	C1-C2-C5	C1-C3-C4	C1	2
C2	C2-C5	C1-C2-C3-C4-C5	C2-C5	1
C3	C1-C2-C3-C4-C5	C3-C4	C3-C4	3
C4	C1-C2-C3-C4-C5	C3-C4	C3-C4	3
C5	C2-C5	C1-C2-C3-C4-C5	C2-C5	1

The hierarchical level results of the ISM analysis are presented in Table 4, with the results highlighted in bold. Based on these results, the interrelationships among the key challenges of digitalization in the construction industry have been identified and are illustrated in Figure 1. The first level of the hierarchy consists of "Applications (C3)" and "Company Management (C4)."

Figure 1: Interpretive Structural Modeling of the Key Challenges of Digitalization in the Construction Industry

The results of the Interpretive Structural Modeling indicate that the challenges begin with "Applications (C3)" and "Company Management (C4)" and continue with "Professionals (Users – C1)." At the highest level of the hierarchy, "Workers (C2)" and "Construction Site Management (C5)" were identified.

4 CONCLUSION

Although Industry 4.0 continues to evolve, the construction industry has yet to fully adopt its principles. The sector continues to face significant challenges, particularly in adopting the digitalization processes that form the foundation of Industry 4.0.

This study aimed to identify and structure the key challenges to digitalization within the construction industry in a hierarchical manner. Through a comprehensive literature review, five key challenges were identified: Professionals (Users – C1), Workers (C2), Applications (C3), Company Management (C4), and Construction Site Management (C5). A structured questionnaire was designed based on these variables and completed by five industry experts. The data collected were analyzed using Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) to explore the interrelationships among the challenges and to develop a hierarchical structure.

The ISM results revealed that the first level of the hierarchy consists of Applications (C3) and Company Management (C4), which act as foundational drivers. These are followed by Professionals (Users – C1) at the second level, and finally, Workers (C2) and Construction Site Management (C5) at the top level, indicating their strong dependency on the lower-tier elements.

These findings suggest that one of the initial challenges that must be addressed in the digitalization of the construction industry is overcoming the issues encountered in the use of digital applications and ensuring that top management adopts and supports these practices. Within this framework, the mandatory implementation of BIM in construction projects in the United Kingdom—recognized as a pivotal step in the digital transformation of the sector—serves as an illustrative example of early-stage efforts aimed at overcoming the Applications (C3) and Company Management (C4) challenges situated at the foundational level of the hierarchical model proposed in this study. This underscores the potential of regulatory and legal instruments to serve as key enablers in addressing these critical barriers. Furthermore, the challenges identified at the second and third levels of the hierarchy are considered manageable through training that enhances knowledge and skills related to digitalization and practical applications in the industry.

The gradual resolution of each challenge within the hierarchical structure identified in this study—and its systematic integration into the construction sector—is likely to facilitate the industry's adaptation to digital transformation, while also mitigating potential risks that may emerge throughout

the process. For companies operating within the construction industry, it can be concluded that the initial step toward digital transformation should involve increasing managerial awareness and fostering a comprehensive understanding of the significance of digital applications. In the subsequent phase, companies should focus on raising awareness and providing training for professionals who will be directly involved in the implementation of these digital tools. Finally, the integration of such applications into site management practices—along with efforts to improve workers' awareness and understanding—can play a crucial role in overcoming the fundamental challenges associated with digitalization.

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